

Energy-Entropy, Thermodynamics and Function-Inverse Function Pairs

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Recently in the literature, various derivations of entropies such as Tsallis entropy and Kaniadakis entropy have appeared using extremization of a Shannon like entropy expression or the thermodynamic relationship $dE=TdS$ ((1)). In a series of notes, we have argued that Shannon's, Tsallis' and Kaniadakis' entropies and distributions as a function of energy are related to function-inverse pairs. In this note, we wish to consider ((1)) in a general way to show this relationship between function and inverse functions pairs. In particular, we wish to show that for the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Juttner, Kaniadakis and Tsallis distributions, $E_{\text{internal}} = TS$ with function-inverse function pairs used to create S , the entropy. From this, $dE=TdS$ follows with T being a placeholder because $f(e/T)$.

Average Internal Energy

Consider the case of average energy:

$$\langle e \rangle = \int de e f(e/T) \quad ((2))$$

(In some cases the integral may not be over de , for example for a gas, it usually ranges over d^3p although $f(e)$ remains the same. The average energy may be changed in various ways. If there are external parameters such as volume, one may obtain a work term $-PdV$ associated with dE . Similar terms exist for other external parameters. It is possible, however, to change the average energy without changing any external parameters. In thermodynamics, one usually describes this increase or decrease as due to "heat". In general, it seems that in such a case $f(e)$ changes to $f(e)+df(e)$ as shown in (1). In general, as shown in (1):

$$\int de f(e)=1 \text{ so: } \int de df(e) = 0 \quad ((3))$$

Thus, in thermodynamics one has for a change in internal energy with external parameters fixed:

$$de = TdS$$

At this point, we wish to do two things:

1. Introduce a parameter T , the temperature, related to average energy. We then express $f(e)$ as $f(e/T)$ which seems to be the convention in the literature.. A main point we wish to stress is that:

$$df = df/dT dT \quad ((5))$$

Thus, the change in internal energy is due to the change in T. The distribution is a function of e/T so it changes as well.

2. Use the idea of a function-inverse function pair $Q(f)$ and $f(e/T)$. Thus, $Q(f(e/T)) = e/T$.

Next, we wish to apply this idea of a function-inverse function pair to the average internal energy: In the literature, it seems $de = TdS$ is often used as a starting point, but we wish to show entropy seems to be directly related to internal energy if one makes use of function-inverse function pairs.

Average internal energy = $e_{ave} = \int de e f(e)$

Introduce a function Q such that $Q(g(e/T)) = e/T$ where $B g(e/T)$ is the energy distribution, B being a normalization factor. For the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Juttner and Kaniadakis cases such pairs exist and are used. The Tsallis case is also similar. Then:

$$E_{ave} = \int de e^{-T} f(e) Q(g(e/T)) \quad ((4))$$

Here, $f(e) = 1/(A_0 T) g(e/T)$ where A_0 is a constant. Given that:

$\int de f(e) = 1 = B \int de g(e/T)$ where B is a normalization factor, then $B = 1/(A_0 T)$ where $A_0 = \int dx g(x)$. Similarly, T should be related to e_{ave} by:

$$E_{ave} = \int de e f(e) = 1/(A_0 T) \int dx x g(x) = C_1 T \quad ((5))$$

Thus, if one associates $-T (1/A_0 T) f(e) Q(g(e/T))$ with an entropy density (which is what is ultimately done in the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Juttner, Kaniadakis and Tsallis cases), the “thermodynamic” equation ((4)) equates internal energy and entropy directly.

For the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Juttner cases, $g(e/T) = \exp(-e/T)$ and Q is minus the natural log. If one insists on keeping B and $g(e/T)$ together, then for the Maxwell-Boltzmann case one would write:

$$\int de (T) f(e) \ln[Bg(e/T)] = \int de (T) f(e) \ln(g(e/T)) + \int de (T) f(e) \ln[1/(A_0 T)]$$

The second integral on the RHS is a constant because $\int de f(e) = 1$. Thus, perhaps one deals with ((1)) in thermodynamics to eliminate this constant. It seems, however, that the forms of some of the entropies used in literature are related to function-inverse function pairs which are related to $e_{ave} = TS$.

From ((5)), we argue that changing energy by changing f by changing T should be the same for both sides of the equation. Consider explicitly changing:

$$\int de f(T) Q(g(e/T)) = \int de df e + \int de f dT e/T + \int de f T dQ/df df/dx (-e dT/T^2) \quad ((7))$$

The first integral on the RHS already represents the change in the internal energy, so the last two integrals should add to zero. (In general, $T Q(g(e/T))=e$ and so would not be involved in a change due to T in the first place.)

For the third integral on the RHS we use:

$$Q(f(x))=x \text{ so } dQ/df (df/dx) = 1 \text{ or } dQ/df = df/dx^{-1} \quad ((8))$$

Relationship ((8)) may be verified for the MB, Juttner and Kaniadakis cases.

Thus, the two last integrals vanish. By starting with a form of e internal = $\int de f(e) (T) Q(f(e/T))$ and choosing Q and f to inverse functions such that $Q(g(e/T))=e/T$ where $f(e)=Bg(e/T)$, one may obtain the thermodynamic relation $dE=TdS$ ((1)).

We have used T as a placeholder in the definition of entropy $f(e) (T) Q(f(e/T))$ because f is a function of e/T . It serves to cancel the $1/T$ associated with e . It may be noted that $de=TdS$ applies to an ideal gas. In such a case, $S(V,T,N)$. Holding V and N constant means dS changes as dT , so it seems the T multiplier of dS is also a placeholder.

For the Tsallis case treated in (1), matters are slightly different, but the function-inverse function idea still seems to apply. For instance, $f(e/T)=B(e/T)^{-w}$ ((9)). The inverse function Q is $g^{-1/w}$. Thus, the corresponding entropy according to the ideas above would be:

$$\int de (-T) f^{-1/w}. \quad ((10))$$

$$\text{In (1), the result is given as : } S= C1(1- \int de f^{-1/w}) \quad ((11))$$

((10)) and ((11)) are very similar, with ((11)) containing an added constant.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have tried to argue that (T) times entropy i.e. $T fQ(g)$ (where $f=Bg(e/T)$ with B being a normalization constant), and Q being the inverse function of $g(e/T)$ is equivalent to the average energy at least for the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Juttner and Kaniadakis distributions and even the Tsallis case. In other words, one may directly associate e internal ave = $\int de f(e/T) e$ with the entropy i.e. e ave = $\int de f(e/T) (T) Q(g(e/T))$. From this expression, one may obtain the thermodynamic result $dE=TdS$.

References

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